

Replicating Attribute Amnesia Effect in the Single-Stimulus Design

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This report is drafted based on the pre-registration of this experiment (Zheng et al., 2022).

Introduction

Attribute Amnesia refers to the phenomenon that subjects fail to report some features (e.g., colour) of a stimulus after they have been asked to repetitively report some other features (e.g., numeric parity) of the same stimulus (Chen & Wyble, 2015). This effect has shown strong replicability in the multi-stimuli design, in which there are normally one target among three distractors stimuli. Recently, Wang et al. (2021) furtherly showed the robustness of this effect when there was only one stimulus on the screen. As the main experiment of the current project will be conducted online, we aim to pre-register replication attempt of Experiment 1 of Wang et al. (2021) in the online-experiment setting.

The effect to replicate

(Parity-Color Effect) Subjects are asked to repetitively report the parity of a coloured Arabic number on the first 27 trials (pre-surprise trials). On the 28th trial (surprise trial), subjects are surprisingly asked to report the colour of the Arabic number they have just seen before the parity task. The same procedure applies to the following four trials (control trials). In Wang et al. (2021), the memory performance of colour on the surprise trial was significantly lower than that on the first control trial (attribute amnesia effect).

Motivation of the replication

All the future experiments of the current project will be conducted online. However, the existing literature only showed the robustness of attribute amnesia in the offline lab settings. Therefore, it is vital for us to replicate the existing attribute amnesia effect online before further experimentation. Also, previous attribute amnesia literature only showed this effect in a very small sample size (normally 20). Large effect size of attribute amnesia might be less trustworthy with small sample size. We aim to replicate in a relatively large sample size ($N=100$). The effect size of the effect I am trying to replicate is $d' = 1.206$ 95% CI (0.483, 1.930), $N = 20$. The original study was conducted on a computer in lab at Zhejiang University in China.

Method

Design

The experiment was programmed on Labvanced and the original code is openly accessible (<https://www.labvanced.com/page/library/33152>).

Figure 1: Every trial started with a 10-s five-dot eye-tracking re-calibration. The instruction of parity task follows: Please get ready to press E or O on your keyboard to report the parity of the number as QUICKLY and ACCURATELY as possible. Press E for an even number. Press O for an odd number. Press the space bar to start the trial when you are ready. The duration of fixation cross was randomly sampled between 1000 and 2000 ms. The stimulus remains on the screen until the participant makes response to the parity of the number. Since the 28th trial, a 500 ms blank screen follows the stimulus display and precedes the surprise task (i.e., color task) instruction.

The assumptions (e.g., about the meaning of the stimuli) in the original study will also hold in my replication because the stimulus used in this experiment will be Arabic numbers (12-19) in four different colours (red, green, yellow, and purple). These materials are equally comprehensible for subjects from China (where original data collection took place) and from the other parts of the world. Location of the experimenter during data collection will be Germany, but the data collection will take place online. The location of participants could be outside of Germany. Given the fact that the data will be collected online, experimenter have very little knowledge of participant experimental condition. However, this experiment demands that the experiment could only be conducted on a computer, and head movements and eye movements will be recorded and constrained during the experiment. Otherwise, the experiment will be interrupted. Therefore, the experimenter is aware of the overall hypotheses but will not have direct contact with participants during the experiment. The target sample size of the replication is 100. The rationale for my sample size is that the existing literature of attribute amnesia has been based on very small sample size ($N=20$), which disables us from getting a robust and an accurate effect size of the effect. We, therefore, aim to estimate the effect size of attribute amnesia with a sample size of 100. As this replication will be conducted online, the experimental condition will be harder to control than lab experiments. This might influence the effect size of attribute amnesia. However, it is hard to estimate whether this may reduce or enlarge the effect size. If we fail to replicate the effect online, we will aim to replicate it offline with a relatively smaller sample size ($N=30$).

Analysis

The data exclusion criteria is: 1. parity judgement accuracy on the pre-surprise trials is lower than 82% (more than 5 error trials in 27 pre-surprise trials); 2. head movements during experiment leads to calibration failure. The analysis plan is: 1. Compute average task 1 accuracy in pre-surprise trials for each subjects; 2. Check fixation on target on the pre-surprise and surprise trials; 3. Use Chi-square test to compare memory performance of surprise attribute on surprise trial with that on the first control trial; 4. Use Chi-square test to compare memory performance of surprise attribute on surprise trial with chance-level performance (25%); 5. Use Chi-square test to compare memory performance of surprise attribute on surprise trial with performance of Wang et al. (35%).

A successful replication is defined as: 1. Pre-surprise average performance higher than 90%; 2. The p-value of Chi-square test in Analysis 3 is lower than 0.05; 3. The p-value of Chi-square test in Analysis 5 is NOT* lower than 0.05.

Results

Figure 2: Presurprise accuracy, RT and surprise performance.

As shown in Fig.2A, the average performance on the pre-surprise task was indeed higher than 90% (92.058%). The average RT to the pre-surprise task was 722.020 ms (SE = 18.172). Participants indeed fixated on the stimulus during stimulus display (Fig.2C). There is significant attribute amnesia effect after excluding invalid participants given the significant difference in surprise task performance on the surprise trial (54.945%) and that on the first control trial (90.110%, X-squared = 28.238, $p = 0.000$). The surprise performance on the surprise trial was significantly higher than chance performance (X-squared = 50.000, $p = 0.000$). The attribute amnesia effect in this online experiment (35.165%) is not significantly different from that reported in Wang et al (2021) (55.000%, X-squared = 2.718, $p = 0.099$).

Exploratory Analysis

The first exploratory analysis in Fig. 3A shows the surprise performance when the color is red (~80%) is much higher than otherwise (~45%) (red vs green: $z = -2.466$, $p = 0.014$; red vs purple: $z = -2.466$, $p = 0.014$; red vs yellow: $z = -2.066$, $p = 0.039$). We suspect this is due to the fact that red bar in the surprise task instruction is too close to the display location of the stimulus. The memory trace of red color representation was re-boosted upon such repetition in the foveal vision.

Furthermore, as shown in Fig. 3B, we found that surprise performance is correlated with response time to pre-surprise attribute on the surprise trial ($z = 2.301$, $p = 0.021$). This might be due to the fact that longer display time of the stimulus leads to stronger memory trace in task-irrelevant features.

Figure 3: The effect of color and presurprise RT

Conclusion

This study shows that one can indeed replicate previous in-lab experiment on attribute amnesia in the online setting, demonstrating convincing online data quality for serious investigations. The functions of Webcam-based eyetracking from Labvanced also make rigorous environmental control and recording saccadic data possible.

Reference

- Zheng, Z., Melloni, L., Trubutschek, D., & Chen, X. (2022). Replicating Attribute Amnesia Effect in the Single-Stimulus Design. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/4NF7Q>
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